

Proceedings of 8th Transport Research Arena TRA 2020, April 27-30, 2020, Helsinki, Finland

RAGTIME holistic governance management tool for multimodal transport infrastructures

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Abstract

RAGTIME governance management tool is a risk-based approach for multimodal Transport Infrastructure Asset Management. The governance tool implements a whole system planning software platform able to facilitate a holistic management throughout the entire lifecycle of infrastructures. The development is based on multi-scale data model that uses a risk-based approach, incorporating resilient concepts and mitigation actions to support infrastructure stakeholders during its whole life-cycle by fostering an electronic Tender Process procurement mechanism that promotes the transparency and efficiency, while reducing the risks of the process.

Keywords: Infrastructure governance; risk management; asset management optimization; multicriteria evaluation; structural health monitoring.

1. Introduction

RAGTIME is a research and development project that aims to develop, demonstrate and validate innovative management approaches. The governance tool developed for the platform includes a whole system planning software able to facilitate the holistic management of multimodal infrastructure networks process throughout its entire lifecycle. RAGTIME is based on standard multi-scale data models that provide an integrated view with a risk-based approach. The platform implements risk-based models, resilient concepts and mitigation actions, with specific reference to climate change related threats perspectives, monitored with smart systems, in order to be able to propose and implement effective mitigation actions.

The RAGTIME Governance Module was designed and implemented to support infrastructure owners and contractors manage the assets pertaining to an infrastructure project during its whole life-cycle. The development has grouped the process requirements for the main infrastructure lifecycle phases as: Evaluation & Decision,

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Design & Construction and Operation & Maintenance. The output fosters a transparent electronic procurement mechanism or “Tender Process” able to perform risk based multi-criteria evaluations. These main processes developed to improve the governance during the different life-cycle phases are described below:

- *Tender Process*: This process will result in a flexible, transparent and fair path for the rest of the module. By leveraging this life-cycle supporting process, the infrastructure owners can easily define tenders for different types of stakeholders, such as contractors and concessionaires. To achieve this objective the first step of the process includes a tender definition establishing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) descriptions and assessment weights carried out by the owner/tender proposal. During the next step the interested contractors declare their capabilities to carry out the works by filling their proposed valued KPIs. When the tender is over, the winning contractor is selected transparently by the procurement system via the application of a multi-criteria analysis service. At the end of the process, the owner notifies the winning contractor, who can start a new governance process. All the transactions generated during the procurement process are stored in a master registry that can be consulted to resolve possible litigations during the contract awarding process.
- *Evaluation & Decision*: This process lets the administration entities or infrastructure proponents define different infrastructure planning alternatives to solve a certain demand by means of new KPIs and uses the multi-criteria service to select the best alternative. With the selected planning alternative, a feasibility study can be issued to evaluate different alternatives and compare them to the allocated budget allowing a tentative draft project to be issued by the contractor. A new procurement process to select an additional contractor can be launched prior entering the following process.
- *Design & Construction*: This phase will manage the project design and construction awards according to the previously defined specifications. By using the same tender process, the owner can approve the best KPI risk aware process to select the most appropriate contractors. Once the construction work starts, the governance module allows also to control the work certifications. For this step other KPIs are proposed as contract fulfilment elements, to follow-up the different reporting and work acceptance tasks. Once the construction works are finished, a new tender may be launched to involve the Operation & Maintenance management.
- *Operation & Maintenance*: This phase include will include the following tasks: the maintenance contractual agreements, the reporting commencement and control, and the work certifications submitted to the owner. Different related KPIs and reports will be generated and managed by the governance module. The maintenance works imply a continuous assessment of risks and identification of mitigation measures, e.g. the application of Structural Health Monitoring data on predictive models.

2. Governance Methodology.

The RAGTIME Governance Module was implemented following a Business Process Management (BPM) approach. BPM is the activity of representing and modelling processes of an enterprise, so that the current processes may be analysed and improved. The following figures represent the RAGTIME governance workflows (business processes) in Business Process Management Notation (BPMN) format.

Fig. 1 RAGTIME Business Process Management for the Tender process under the Evaluation & Decision phase

- **Evaluation & Decision:** When a new project (infrastructure) is to be planned, designed and executed, the owner and the contractors will follow this sequence of activities:
 1. The owner defines the KPIs and weights for a new tender process (this process might be linked in a future to electronic public tender services, like TED fostered by the EC)
 2. The interested contractors apply for the tender and declare their capabilities to carry out the works (through filling in the KPIs defined by the owner)
 3. After the allotted tender time, the offers are evaluated automatically and the winning contractor is selected by the system transparently, allowing the owner and the contractor sign the contract
 4. The winning contractor defines several planning alternatives for building the infrastructure (filling in some KPIs) and a multi-criteria service is used to select the best one. With the selected planning alternative, a feasibility study is issued by the contractor to evaluate different alternatives. As a result, a tentative draft is issued by the contractor
 5. For the general case, a public contract is enforced prior to entering the Design & Construction phase. In this case, a new contractor tender is launched as in point number 1.
 6. As a result, the winning contractor is selected and the Design & Construction workflow is assigned to them.

Fig. 2 Design & Construction phase

- **Design & Construction:** During this phase, the project is designed and constructed by the contractor and supervised by the administration. Some KPIs are used to follow-up the different reporting tasks. Once the construction works are finished, a new tender is launched to select the Operation & Maintenance manager.

Fig. 3 Operation & Maintenance phase

- *Operation & Maintenance*: This phase includes the following tasks: the maintenance start, the start-up report and the work certifications. Some KPIs are generated that will feed the different reports generated by the different actors involved in the process.

3. Business Process Management (BPM)

A workflow engine, as part of a BPM suite, is a software application that executes BPMN business processes. It is a key component in workflow technology and typically makes use of a database server. A workflow engine manages and monitors the state of tasks in a workflow and guides the involved actors in the follow-up of the workflow. The engine determines which task to transition according to the sequence flows defined in the BPMN model.

There are two types of tasks: manual tasks that involve the interaction of users through application forms and service tasks, which are automated tasks that interface with external systems (e.g. ESBs) and provide logic for the workflow. For example, a manual task would comprise the definition of tender KPIs by the owner or the filling in their values by the contractors. An example of a service (automated) task would be the multi-criteria logic to apply to select the most appropriate offer to win a bidding tender.

The workflow engine facilitates the flow of information, tasks, and events. Workflow engines mainly have three functions:

- *Check process status*: To activate and assign manual tasks to users depending on the defined status and the sequence flows.
- *Authority of users*: To check if the current user is authorised to execute the task.
- *Condition gateways*: To be used to modify the execution path during runtime based on workflow-generated process variables.

In the context of project RAGTIME, the IT Governance was implemented as a BPMS software suite providing the following tools:

- *Ragtime IDM (Identity Management Tool)*: Provides user authentication and authorization. This tool enables single sign-on capabilities to the rest of the applications, providing a central place to define users, groups and privileges
- *Ragtime Modeler Tool*: Provides a BPMN process modelling tool that allows business analysts and IT developers sketch up, develop and deploy business processes into the RAGTIME workflow engine (aka Ragtime Governance Module)
- *Ragtime IT Governance Module*: Provides a workflow engine where the deployed models are executed by the stakeholders. With this application, new process instances can be started and tasks can be completed. This tool provides a Document Management System that allows the attachment of documents tasks to enable document review processes

4. Functionalities of RAGTIME IT Governance Module

The functionalities of the IT Governance suite are explained following a simplified use case scenario. Let's demonstrate the *Evaluation & Decision* phase. Let's assume that the *owner of a ROAD infrastructure* (the administration) intends to plan, design and execute a new infrastructure project with the following characteristics:

- *What*: Arterial Highway connections in Cantabria
- *When*: Next 4 years
- *Who*: National government to cover not-well connected areas with high demand due to second residence and tourism
- *Which*:
 - Proposal A: Highway connection to *Comillas*: Population - Comillas Area (Comillas, Alfoz de Lloredo, Ruiloba, Udías), Residents: 6.362 inhabitants, Summer: 31.810 people
 - Proposal B: Highway connection to *Somo*: Population - Somo Area (Ribamontán al Mar, Ribamontán al Monte, Marina de Cudeyo, Bareyo), Residents: 13.906, Summer: 69.530 people

The infrastructure owner uses the *Weighted Decision Matrix* (WDM) shown in Fig.4, to select the KPIs and weights to be applied during the definition of the Tender KPIs (the definition is carried out in the first manual task of the Tender Process).

LIFE CYCLE PROJECT by Governance		KPI %	WEIGHT OF WEIGHT	CRITERIA					WEIGHT OF APPROX. WEIGHT
				DIRTY	EFFICIENT	RESILIENT	SOCIAL INCLUSIVE	SAFE DECISION	
CATALOG	TENDER	ECONOMICAL OFFER	70%		1				2.80%
		WARRANTY TERM	75%			1			2.93%
		CURRICULUM VITAE PERSONAL	70%			1			2.80%
		TECHNICAL MEANS	57.5%			1			2.29%
		OUTSOURCING	80%			1			3.20%
		SYSTEMS	80%	1				1	3.20%
		OBJECTIVES	100%				1		3.94%
		CRITERIA	100%				1		3.94%
		PROPRIETIES	75%				1		2.93%
		FEASIBILITY	75%				1		2.93%
PLAN	TENDER	ECONOMICAL OFFER	70%		1				2.80%
		WARRANTY TERM	75%			1			2.93%
		CURRICULUM VITAE PERSONAL	70%			1			2.80%
		TECHNICAL MEANS	57.5%			1			2.29%
		OUTSOURCING	80%			1			3.20%
		SYSTEMS	80%	1				1	3.20%
		OBJECTIVES	100%				1		3.94%
		CRITERIA	100%				1		3.94%
		PROPRIETIES	75%				1		2.93%
		FEASIBILITY	75%				1		2.93%
EVALUATION & DECISION	TENDER	ECONOMICAL OFFER	70%		1				2.80%
		WARRANTY TERM	75%			1			2.93%
		CURRICULUM VITAE PERSONAL	70%			1			2.80%
		TECHNICAL MEANS	57.5%			1			2.29%
		OUTSOURCING	80%			1			3.20%
		SYSTEMS	80%	1				1	3.20%
		OBJECTIVES	100%				1		3.94%
		CRITERIA	100%				1		3.94%
		PROPRIETIES	75%				1		2.93%
		FEASIBILITY	75%				1		2.93%

Fig. 4 Weighted Decision Matrix

The next table shows an example of KPIs that are selected by the infrastructure owner. The number of KPIs that the governance module can handle are not limited.

Table 1. Tender KPIs definition

KPI number	KPI designation	KPI weight
KPI1	ECONOMICAL OFFER	70.0%
KPI2	WARRANTY TERM	75.0%
KPI3	CURRICULUM VITAE PERSONAL	70.0%
KPI4	TECHNICAL MEANS	57.5%
KPI5	SYSTEMS	80.0%

Bearing in mind this KPI definition information, the infrastructure owner (see Figure 5) executes the *Tender Process* to define the characteristics of the tender and launches the bidding process to involve the contractors in the process. Note that the currently logged-in user is presented on the top right corner of the screen.

Fig. 5 Tender Process Execution

The first manual task “Tender definition” allows the owner to define some tender parameters in a form. The workflow of our Tender Process can be seen in the *RAGTIME Modeler Tool*:

Fig. 6 Tender Process BPMN

The next figure shows the “Tender definition” form that is presented to the owner. The parameters that are requested by the form are the tender name, the KPIs definition and the associated weights.

Fig. 7 Tender Definition form

This information is persisted in the database server by the service task named “Persist tender definition.” Next, the flow sequence enters the “Tender application sub-process,” which allows the contractors apply for the electronic tender and stores the tender information in the database server, as shown in Fig. 7. Each of the involved contractors receives a form for applying for the tender, like the one presented in Fig. 8 for the Contractor 1.

Fig. 8 Application for an Electronic Tender form

Each contractor fills in the KPIs defined by the owner and submits the task. All the information about the tender application is persisted for each contractor. Once all the contractors have applied for the tender, or any other condition has fulfilled to exit the sub-process, such as a time event triggering, the flow sequence continues, and the multi-criteria logic is executed by the “Calculate tender ranking” service task. In this use case, there are three Contractors, who provide the tender application details shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Tender KPIs application

Contractor	KPI1 value	KPI2 value	KPI3 value	KPI4 value	KPI5 value
Contractor 1	10.0	8.0	5.0	3.0	2.0
Contractor 2	10.0	9.0	6.0	4.0	3.0
Contractor 3	9.5	7.0	4.0	3.0	2.0

The last task in the workflow, “Review tender ranking”, is assigned to the owner, who will get the results of the tender in an informative form, as displayed in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9 Review tender ranking form

The form contains the results of the ELECTRE multi-criteria analysis comprising the concordance matrix, the discordance matrix, the credibility matrix and the kernel and dominated alternatives (contractors). There is a legend

that maps the alternatives with the contractor names. The figure shows the contractors' ranking according to the kernel and dominated solutions along with the ELECTRE results in text mode. ELECTRE method applied in a collaborative way through a workflow engine enables the simplification of the governance process based on automated decision support capabilities using the governance KPIs to be as transparent as possible during the selection of contractors in a tender process.

According to the results of the ELECTRE multi-criteria method, the winning contractor is Contractor 2. The owner will notify this condition to the winning contractor, who will initiate the *Evaluation & Decision process*. The deployed Evaluation & Decision process can be observed in the RAGTIME Modeler Tool, Fig.10.

Fig. 10 Evaluation & Decision BPMN

Once the Contractor 2 starts the Evaluation & Decision process the flow sequence stops at the first manual task, “Define criteria and objectives.” In this task, the contractor defines the criteria originated by the owner in terms of selection of the best director plan option between Proposal A: Highway connection to Comillas or Proposal B: Highway connection to Somo. The following KPIs are defined by the Contractor 2 based on the owner specifications (see Table 3).

Table 3. Feasibility KPIs definition

KPI number	KPI designation	KPI weight
KPI1	Investment level with respect to the budget availability	0.17
KPI2	Improvements with respect to the Bidding Budget	0.04
KPI3	Budget of social measures respect to Bidding Budget	0.17
KPI4	Monthly Debt Coverage respect to Total Debt	0.18
KPI5	Improvements with respect to the Bidding Budget	0.05

The “Define criteria and objectives” allows Contractor 2 to define the parameters shown in fig. 11: Project name - Identifier of the director plan, Budget available - Available public funding, Number of alternatives - Proposal A: Highway connection to Comillas and Proposal B: Highway connection to Somo, KPI definition and weights - Multi-criteria definition.

Fig. 11 Define criteria and objectives form

Once the criteria are defined, the data is saved in the database server. Once the viability data is persisted, the flow sequence enters a sub-process used to issue the KPIs associated to the two alternatives. Within this sub-process, the Contractor 2 fills in the forms associated to the “Calculate KPIs for all options” task. The form contains the following fields: feasible option name of the alternative: Comillas or Somo, total cost for each alternative, KPIs for each alternative, and profitability of the alternative. In this use case, there are two alternatives or proposals, which gather the next KPI information (see Table 4).

Table 4. Feasibility KPIs application

Proposals	KPI1 value	KPI2 value	KPI3 value	KPI4 value	KPI5 value
A-Comillas	10.0	8.0	5.0	3.0	2.0
B-Somo	10.0	9.0	6.0	4.0	3.0

The form where the contractor introduces the information related to the proposals is shown in Fig.12.

Fig. 12 Calculate KPIs for all options form

The data for each of the submitted option forms is persisted in the database server. Once the two alternatives have been issued by the contractor, the “Select options by multicriteria” service task is executed. The next task in the workflow, “Review Viability Results,” shows the results of the viability evaluation in an informative form, as displayed in Fig.13.

Review Viability Results			
Assignee: Contractor 2 Due: No due date Part of process: Evaluation and Decision - July 23rd 2018 Ended: a day ago Duration: 27 seconds			
No people involved No content items No comments No sub tasks Show details			
Project Name: Arterial Highway connections in Cantabria			
Concordance Matrix:		a1	a2
	a1	0.0	0.2787
	a2	1.0	0.0
Discordance Matrix:		a1	a2
	a1	0.0	1.0
	a2	0.0	0.0
Credibility Matrix:		a1	a2
	a1	0.0	0.0
	a2	1.0	0.0
Kernel:	a2		
Dominated:	a1		

Fig. 13 Review Viability Results form

The form contains the results of the ELECTRE multi-criteria analysis comprising the concordance matrix, the discordance matrix, the credibility matrix and the kernel and dominated alternatives (proposals). There is a legend that maps the alternatives with the alternative names. The alternatives ranking is also shown according to the kernel and dominated solutions from the method. According to the results of the ELECTRE multi-criteria method, the winning alternative is Proposal B: Highway connection to Somo.

Once the results are visualized, the flow sequence enters a decision tree, where a feasibility study is made to check the proposal budget availability compared to allocated budget. In this case, the alternative falls below available public funding issued by the owner, therefore the flow sequence will reach the “Public Contract” task where the Contractor will be informed that the winning option (Somo) is suitable for public contract, as shown in Fig.14.

Fig. 14 Public contract issuing

The final task shown in Fig.15, “Proposed Draft,” informs the user that the proposed option should go to public contract and, therefore, a draft for the project Arterial Highway connections in Cantabria (Somo) should be created and appended to the workflow (see picture below), leveraging the Document Content management capabilities of the Ragtime Governance Module. A new Tender Process could be required to select a contractor who will handle the Design & Construction and ulterior phases.

Fig. 15 Proposed Draft

This concludes the Evaluation & Decision use case that demonstrates the multi-user collaborative approach fostered by the governance module and the decision support capabilities of its multi-criteria analysis.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the European Commission under the H2020 programme, for the project RAGTIME (Risk based approaches for Asset inteGrity multimodal Transport Infrastructure ManagEmEnt). This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690660. This paper reflects only the author’s views. The European Commission and INEA are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. In addition, we would like to thank Claire Mathews for her invaluable contribution.

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